

MSProfileR report

I. Data loading

- Number of spectra loaded: 344

II. Preprocessing

Trimming

Parameters

- Minimum mass: 2000 m/z
- Maximum mass: 20000 m/z

Results

Conformity test

Results

Criteria	Results
Number of empty spectra	0
Number of irregular spectra	0
Number of different lengths	0

Parameters

- Exclude empty spectra: Yes
- Exclude irregular spectra: Yes

Cleaning

Parameters

- Method used to transform intensity: Sqrt
- Method used to smooth intensity: Savitsky-Golay
- Half window size: 10
- Method used to remove baseline: SNIP
- Number of iterations: 100
- Method used to calibrate intensity: TIC

Results

18_thorax_Aedes_impiger [B10]

Quality control

Parameters

- Scale estimator: Q
- Method used for the identification of atypical spectra: RC
- Threshold: 3
- Include lower spectra: Yes

Results

- Number of typical spectra: 328/344

- Number of atypical spectra: 16/344
- Atypical spectra: 16: Ctrl3_thorax_Aedes_aegypti [H4], 82: 42_thorax_Aedes_exrucians [D11], 138: 56_thorax_Aedes_hexodontus [E6], 152: 59_thoraxAedes_hexodontus [E8], 217: 06_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A10], 218: 06_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A11], 219: 06_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A12], 225: 08_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A5], 289: 81_thorax_Aedes_pullatus [G10], 313: 65_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F5], 314: 65_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F6], 320: 66_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F9], 328: 68_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F8], 329: 69_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F10], 330: 69_thorax_Aedes_punctor [F11], 339: 71_thoraxAedes_punctor [F7]

Averaging

Parameters

- Method: Mean

Results

- Number of spectra before merging: 328
- Number of spectra after merging: 86

III. Processing

Peak detection

Parameters

- Noise estimator method: MAD
- Half window size:
- SNR: 3

Results

Average number of peaks for SNR 3: 91.35 (sd: 9.31)

01_thorax_Aedes_nigripes [A1 A2 A3 A4]

Spectrum alignment

Parameters

- Method for reference peaks: MAD
- Minimum frequency of reference peaks: 0.5
- Tolerance for reference peaks: 0.002
- Warping method for alignment: Lowess

Results

- Number of reference peaks: 29

Peak binning

Parameters

- Method for binning: Strict
- Tolerance for reference binning: 0.002

Results

Number of peaks: 637

Peak filtering

Parameters

- Minimum frequency: 0.2

Results

Number of peaks: 160

Intensity matrix

Parameters

- Fill missing intensities using the aligned spectra: Yes

Results

